

Interview and background data on Livonian language transmission

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Fundamental and Applied Research project (Latvia) "Continuity of Livonian: Understanding language transmission processes in a critically endangered contemporary indigenous community to develop process-driven instruments for preservation and revitalisation" (Nr. lzp-2023/1-0264).

Data collection includes interviews, background data and relations of Livonian speakers, community and participants of Livonian data transmission processes.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

FLPP "Continuity of Livonian: Understanding language transmission processes in a critically endangered contemporary indigenous community to develop process-driven instruments for preservation and revitalisation" (lzp-2023/1-0264)

Researchers

Gunta Klava (0000-0003-1049-9426), Valts Ernštreits (0000-0002-5323-8536), Bridget Moran-Nae

Organizations

University of Latvia Livonian Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Interview and background data on Livonian language transmission

Description:

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Fundamental and Applied Research project (Latvia) "Continuity of Livonian: Understanding language transmission processes in a critically endangered contemporary indigenous community to develop process-driven instruments for preservation and revitalisation" (Nr. lzp-2023/1-0264).

Data collection includes interviews, background data and relations of Livonian speakers, community and participants of Livonian data transmission processes.

Researchers:

Gunta Klava (0000-0003-1049-9426)

Valts Ernštreits (0000-0002-5323-8536)

Bridget Moran-Nae

Organizations:

University of Latvia Livonian Institute

Contact: Ernštreits Valts (valts.ernstreits@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: FLPP "Continuity of Livonian: Understanding language transmission processes in a critically endangered contemporary indigenous community to develop process-driven instruments for preservation and revitalisation" (lzp-2023/1-0264)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Interview and background data on Livonian language transmission

Data collection includes interviews, background data and relations of Livonian speakers, community and participants of Livonian data transmission processes.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Textual data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- MP3
- Others

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Additional data will be collected from publications, manuscripts and other sources.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociolinguists, intangible culture researchers and others.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Valts Ernštreits (0000-0002-5323-8536)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Privacy constraints
- Privacy policies

Powered by

